

A. LLM-based Structure Extraction Prompt for the Mapping Study

We use gemini-3-flash-preview to extract structured information about interpretable machine learning (IML) evaluation and reporting practices from full-text genomics papers. The whole pipeline can be divided into two stages. At the first stage, we use a few-shot in-context learning approach to extract the structured information from the paper. At the second stage, we use a self-reflection pass to verify the extraction against the actual paper text and correct any errors.

A.1. Stage 1: Few-shot In-context Learning for Structured Extraction

A.1.1. SYSTEM INSTRUCTION

You are a rigorous scientific information extraction assistant. Your task is to read a full-text research paper from the field of genomics / computational biology and extract structured information about how interpretable machine learning (IML) methods are used, evaluated, and reported in the paper.

You must extract ONLY information that is explicitly stated or directly inferable from the paper text. Do NOT guess, speculate, or hallucinate information. If a field cannot be determined from the paper, mark it as "unclear".

A.1.2. TASK PROMPT

Below is the full text of a research paper from genomics / computational biology. Please carefully read the entire paper and extract the following structured information about its use of interpretable machine learning (IML) methods.

Definitions

Interpretable Machine Learning (IML) methods include any technique used to explain, interpret, or understand the predictions or internal representations of a machine learning model. Common examples in genomics include (but are not limited to):

- Feature attribution methods: Saliency Maps, DeepLIFT, Integrated Gradients (IG), In Silico Mutagenesis (ISM), DeepSHAP, SHAP, SmoothGrad, GradCAM, Guided Backpropagation, LIME
- Interaction methods: Integrated Hessians, DFIM (Deep Feature Interaction Maps), SQUID
- Attention-based interpretation: attention weight visualization, attention rollout
- Concept-based methods: TCAV, concept bottleneck models
- Model-specific interpretation: first-layer filter visualization, motif extraction from convolutional filters
- Other post-hoc or intrinsic interpretability approaches

Validation of IML outputs refers to any step the authors take to assess whether the IML-derived explanations are correct, meaningful, or reliable. This includes:

- **Visual inspection**: Authors or domain experts visually examine IML outputs (e.g., attribution maps, highlighted regions) and qualitatively judge whether they "make sense" or align with known biology.
- **Querying databases**: Authors compare IML outputs against entries in biological databases (e.g., JASPAR, ENCODE, UniProt, Gene Ontology, KEGG) to check whether highlighted features correspond to known biological entities.
- **Synthetic datasets**: Authors use synthetic or simulated data with known ground-truth signals to test whether the IML method can recover those signals.
- **Wet-lab experiments**: Authors perform laboratory experiments (e.g., mutagenesis assays, CRISPR perturbations, reporter assays, ChIP-qPCR) to validate IML-derived predictions.
- **Others**: Any other validation strategy not covered above (e.g., comparison with other computational predictions, consistency checks, perturbation-based faithfulness tests).

Successful instance: A specific case, example, or result that the authors present where the IML output aligns with known biology or expected behavior. This is

typically shown as a figure or described in text (e.g., "DeepLIFT highlighted the known CTCF binding motif in this sequence").

****Failed instance****: A specific case where the IML output did NOT align with known biology or expected behavior, or where the authors explicitly discuss limitations, errors, or failure modes of the IML method.

Extraction Fields

For the paper provided, extract the following fields:

1. ****iml_methods**** (list of strings): List ALL IML methods used in this paper. Use standardized names where possible (e.g., "DeepLIFT", "Integrated Gradients", "ISM", "SHAP", "LIME", "Attention Weights", "GradCAM", "SmoothGrad", "Filter Visualization", etc.). If the paper uses a custom or novel IML method, use the name given by the authors.
2. ****iml_method_count**** (integer): The total number of distinct IML methods used. Count each method once, even if applied to multiple models or datasets.
3. ****iml_justification**** (string, one of: "yes", "no", "unclear"): Did the authors provide an explicit justification for why they chose the specific IML method(s)? A justification means a stated reason (e.g., "we used DeepLIFT because it satisfies the completeness axiom" or "we chose SHAP due to its theoretical guarantees"). Simply naming the method without a reason does NOT count as a justification.
4. ****validation_types**** (list of strings): List ALL types of validation the authors performed on their IML outputs. Use ONLY these categories: "visual_inspection", "querying_databases", "synthetic_datasets", "wet_lab_experiments", "others". If validation involves multiple types, list all that apply. If no validation was performed, use ["none"].
5. ****num_successful_instances**** (integer 0-5, or "6+", or "unclear"): How many distinct successful instances (specific examples where IML outputs aligned with known biology) are reported in the paper? Count each unique example once. If the count is 6 or more, output "6+". If the authors report aggregate statistics over many instances without showing individual examples, record "0" for individual instances. If unclear, use "unclear".
6. ****failure_reported**** (string, one of: "yes", "no"): Did the authors report ANY cases where the IML method failed, produced unexpected results, or did not align with known biology? Also counts if the authors discuss limitations or failure modes of the IML outputs (not just general limitations of the ML model).
7. ****failure_description**** (string or "none"): If failure_reported is "yes", briefly describe what failure was reported. If "no", use "none".

Output Format

Return your answer as a JSON object with the following structure:

```
{
  "iml_methods": [...],
  "iml_method_count": ...,
  "iml_justification": "yes" | "no" | "unclear",
  "validation_types": [...],
  "num_successful_instances": ...,
  "failure_reported": "yes" | "no",
  "failure_description": "... | "none"
}
```

A.1.3. FEW-SHOT DEMONSTRATIONS

Ten manually curated demonstrations are provided below. Each consists of an abbreviated paper description and the corresponding gold-standard extraction (annotated by an author).

```
### Few-Shot Demonstrations

Here are 10 manually curated demonstrations. Each consists of an abbreviated paper
description and the corresponding gold-standard extraction.

#### Demonstration 1

- **Paper description (abbreviated):**
This paper presents a deep learning model for predicting transcription factor binding
from DNA sequence. The model is a convolutional neural network trained on ChIP-seq
data. After training, the authors apply DeepLIFT to generate per-nucleotide
importance scores. They show three example sequences where the DeepLIFT
attributions highlight the known GATA1 motif (Figures 3A-C). They compare the
highlighted regions against the JASPAR database and note visual agreement. No cases
where DeepLIFT failed to recover a motif are discussed. The authors do not explain
why they chose DeepLIFT over other methods.

- **Gold-standard extraction:**
{
  "iml_methods": ["DeepLIFT"],
  "iml_method_count": 1,
  "iml_justification": "no",
  "validation_types": ["visual_inspection", "querying_databases"],
  "num_successful_instances": 3,
  "failure_reported": "no",
  "failure_description": "none"
}

#### Demonstration 2

- **Paper description (abbreviated):**
This paper develops a transformer-based model for predicting gene expression from
promoter sequences. The authors use three IML methods: Integrated Gradients,
attention weight visualization, and in silico mutagenesis (ISM). They justify their
multi-method approach by stating "we employ multiple interpretability methods to
ensure robustness of our findings." For validation, they construct synthetic
sequences with embedded known motifs and test whether each method recovers them.
They also compare attributions against ENCODE TF binding annotations. They report
12 examples across three figures where methods agree on highlighting the TATA box
and SP1 site. They also report that attention weights failed to localize short
motifs (< 6bp) and discuss this limitation in Section 4.3.

- **Gold-standard extraction:**
{
  "iml_methods": ["Integrated Gradients", "Attention Weights", "ISM"],
  "iml_method_count": 3,
  "iml_justification": "yes",
  "validation_types": ["synthetic_datasets", "querying_databases"],
  "num_successful_instances": "6+",
  "failure_reported": "yes",
  "failure_description": "Attention weights failed to localize short motifs (< 6bp),
discussed in Section 4.3."
}

#### Demonstration 3

- **Paper description (abbreviated):**
```

```
770 This paper introduces a graph neural network for protein function prediction. The
771 authors use GradCAM to highlight important residues. They show one example (Figure
772 5) where GradCAM highlights residues near the active site, and visually inspect it.
773 No database comparison is performed. No other IML methods are used. They mention
774 using GradCAM because "it is widely used" but do not provide a technical
775 justification. No failure cases are reported.
776 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
777 {
778   "iml_methods": ["GradCAM"],
779   "iml_method_count": 1,
780   "iml_justification": "no",
781   "validation_types": ["visual_inspection"],
782   "num_successful_instances": 1,
783   "failure_reported": "no",
784   "failure_description": "none"
785 }
786 ##### Demonstration 4
787 - **Paper description (abbreviated):**
788 This study applies a recurrent neural network to predict RNA secondary structure. To
789 interpret model predictions, the authors use SHAP values and DeepLIFT. They justify
790 SHAP as satisfying game-theoretic axioms and DeepLIFT as computationally efficient.
791 They compare SHAP attributions against known RNA structural motifs from the Rfam
792 database, showing 6 cases of agreement. They also design a synthetic benchmark with
793 planted stem-loop structures and evaluate both methods. They find that SHAP
794 outperforms DeepLIFT on recovering planted signals. They report two cases where
795 DeepLIFT attributions were misleading---highlighting flanking regions instead of
796 the true structural motif---and discuss this as a potential issue with
797 reference-choice sensitivity.
798 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
799 {
800   "iml_methods": ["SHAP", "DeepLIFT"],
801   "iml_method_count": 2,
802   "iml_justification": "yes",
803   "validation_types": ["querying_databases", "synthetic_datasets"],
804   "num_successful_instances": 6,
805   "failure_reported": "yes",
806   "failure_description": "DeepLIFT produced misleading attributions in two cases,
807     highlighting flanking regions instead of true structural motifs. Authors discuss
808     reference-choice sensitivity as the cause."
809 }
810 ##### Demonstration 5
811 - **Paper description (abbreviated):**
812 This paper fine-tunes a genomic foundation model (DNABERT) for variant effect
813 prediction. The authors use Integrated Gradients to visualize which nucleotides
814 contribute to pathogenicity scores. They show two examples where IG attributions
815 overlap with ClinVar-annotated pathogenic variants and visually inspect the
816 attribution maps. No explicit justification for choosing IG is provided. They also
817 perform a perturbation-based sanity check: masking the top-10 attributed positions
818 and observing the prediction drop. They do not report any cases where IG fails. The
819 paper mentions using attention weights in supplementary materials to visualize
820 layer-wise patterns but does not use them for interpretation of specific
821 predictions.
822 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
823 {
824   "iml_methods": ["Integrated Gradients"],
825   "iml_method_count": 1,
```

```
825 "iml_justification": "no",
826 "validation_types": ["visual_inspection", "querying_databases", "others"],
827 "num_successful_instances": 2,
828 "failure_reported": "no",
829 "failure_description": "none"
830 }
831 ##### Demonstration 6
832
833 - **Paper description (abbreviated):**
834 This paper builds an ensemble model for predicting enhancer activity from DNA sequence.
835 No interpretability or explanation methods are applied to the model. The paper
836 focuses entirely on prediction performance (AUROC, AUPRC) across multiple cell
837 types. The word "interpretability" appears only in the abstract in the context of
838 "future work on interpretability."
839
840 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
841 {
842 "iml_methods": [],
843 "iml_method_count": 0,
844 "iml_justification": "unclear",
845 "validation_types": ["none"],
846 "num_successful_instances": 0,
847 "failure_reported": "no",
848 "failure_description": "none"
849 }
850 ##### Demonstration 7
851
852 - **Paper description (abbreviated):**
853 This paper uses a variational autoencoder for single-cell RNA-seq analysis. For
854 interpretability, the authors extract the learned latent space and visualize it
855 with UMAP. They also compute SHAP values to identify genes most influential for
856 cluster assignments. They validate SHAP outputs by cross-referencing the top-ranked
857 genes with known marker genes from the CellMarker database and the Human Protein
858 Atlas. They present 5 cell-type-specific gene lists where the top SHAP genes match
859 known markers. They also note that for two rare cell types, SHAP highlighted genes
860 with no known marker function, which they frame as potentially novel findings
861 rather than failures.
862
863 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
864 {
865 "iml_methods": ["SHAP"],
866 "iml_method_count": 1,
867 "iml_justification": "no",
868 "validation_types": ["querying_databases"],
869 "num_successful_instances": 5,
870 "failure_reported": "no",
871 "failure_description": "none"
872 }
873 ##### Demonstration 8
874
875 - **Paper description (abbreviated):**
876 This paper proposes a new feature attribution method specifically designed for genomic
877 sequence models. The authors benchmark their method against DeepLIFT, Integrated
878 Gradients, ISM, and LIME on transcription factor binding prediction tasks. They use
879 three models (CNN, RNN, Transformer) and five TFs. Validation is performed using
880 known motif annotations from JASPAR and UniBind. They report Perception scores
881 (motif overlap) across all test sequences for each method and present distribution
882 plots. They also perform perturbation-based faithfulness tests (sequential deletion
883 and insertion). They show that their method outperforms baselines on 4 of 5 TFs but
884 fails on SP1 due to GC-content confounding, which they analyze in detail.
```

```

880
881 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
882 {
883   "iml_methods": ["DeepLIFT", "Integrated Gradients", "ISM", "LIME", "authors' novel
884     method"],
885   "iml_method_count": 5,
886   "iml_justification": "yes",
887   "validation_types": ["querying_databases", "others"],
888   "num_successful_instances": 0,
889   "failure_reported": "yes",
890   "failure_description": "The proposed method fails on SP1 due to GC-content
891     confounding. Authors analyze this failure mode in detail."
892 }
893
894 ##### Demonstration 9
895 - **Paper description (abbreviated):**
896 This study trains a multi-task deep learning model to predict histone modifications
897 from DNA sequence. The authors apply SmoothGrad and vanilla saliency maps to
898 visualize important positions for H3K4me3 predictions. They justify SmoothGrad as
899 reducing noise compared to vanilla gradients. They show four example loci where
900 attributions overlap with known promoter elements (visual inspection). They also
901 query the ENCODE database to check if highlighted regions overlap with DNase-seq
902 hypersensitive sites. No failures are mentioned. All four examples are from
903 high-confidence predictions.
904 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
905 {
906   "iml_methods": ["SmoothGrad", "Saliency Maps"],
907   "iml_method_count": 2,
908   "iml_justification": "yes",
909   "validation_types": ["visual_inspection", "querying_databases"],
910   "num_successful_instances": 4,
911   "failure_reported": "no",
912   "failure_description": "none"
913 }
914 ##### Demonstration 10
915 - **Paper description (abbreviated):**
916 This paper applies a pre-trained protein language model to predict protein-protein
917 interactions. For interpretability, the authors extract attention maps from the
918 final transformer layer and visualize them for 10 protein pairs. They also use
919 Integrated Gradients to identify important residues and validate them against known
920 interface residues from the PDB (Protein Data Bank). They report that IG correctly
921 identifies interface residues for 7 out of 10 protein pairs. For the remaining 3
922 pairs, IG highlights allosteric regions distal to the interface, which the authors
923 acknowledge as a limitation and attribute to indirect interaction effects. They
924 chose IG because "it provides a complete attribution that sums to the prediction
925 difference."
926 - **Gold-standard extraction:**
927 {
928   "iml_methods": ["Attention Weights", "Integrated Gradients"],
929   "iml_method_count": 2,
930   "iml_justification": "yes",
931   "validation_types": ["visual_inspection", "querying_databases"],
932   "num_successful_instances": "6+",
933   "failure_reported": "yes",
934   "failure_description": "IG highlights allosteric regions instead of interface
935     residues for 3 out of 10 protein pairs. Authors attribute this to indirect
936     interaction effects."

```

```
}
}
```

A.1.4. INPUT FORMAT

The full text of the paper is provided below the prompt, enclosed in delimiters:

```
<paper>
{FULL_TEXT_OF_PAPER}
</paper>

Now extract the structured information from this paper following the instructions and
output format above.
```

A.2. Stage 2: Self-Reflection Prompt

After Stage 1 returns a JSON extraction for a paper, we will input the paper text and the JSON output back to the LLM to perform the self-reflection. The LLM will re-read the paper and verify each field in the extraction against the actual paper text. It will then correct any hallucinations, miscounts, and misclassifications that slip through Stage 1.

A.2.1. SYSTEM INSTRUCTION

```
You are a meticulous scientific fact-checker. You will be given a research paper and a
structured JSON extraction that was previously produced from that paper. Your job
is to verify every field in the extraction by checking it against the actual paper
text. You must correct any errors you find. Do NOT trust the previous extraction --
treat it as a draft that may contain mistakes.
```

A.2.2. TASK PROMPT

```
Below is a research paper and a JSON extraction that was previously generated from it.
Your task is to carefully verify each field in the extraction against the paper
text.

<paper>
{FULL_TEXT_OF_PAPER}
</paper>

<extraction>
{STAGE_1_JSON_OUTPUT}
</extraction>

For EACH of the 7 fields listed below, perform the following verification steps:

---

#### Field 1: iml_methods

- Re-read the paper and list every interpretable machine learning (IML) method actually
  used (not just mentioned in the related work or future directions).
- For each method in the extraction, find the exact passage in the paper where it is
  applied. If you cannot find such a passage, remove it.
- Check for any IML methods used in the paper that are MISSING from the extraction. If
  found, add them.
- Distinguish between: (a) IML methods applied to explain model predictions, versus (b)
  general analysis tools (e.g., UMAP, PCA, clustering) that are not IML methods,
  versus (c) methods only mentioned in passing, related work, or future directions.
- Only count methods in category (a).
```

```
990
991 **Verification output**: List the corrected iml_methods, and for each method, quote or
992 paraphrase the passage where it is used.
993
994 ---
995 ##### Field 2: iml_method_count
996
997 - Recount based on your verified iml_methods list.
998 - Ensure each method is counted exactly once, even if applied to multiple models,
999 datasets, or tasks.
1000
1001 **Verification output**: Corrected count.
1002
1003 ---
1004 ##### Field 3: iml_justification
1005
1006 - Search the paper for any explicit reason the authors give for choosing their IML
1007 method(s).
1008 - A valid justification includes: theoretical properties (e.g., "satisfies completeness
1009 axiom"), empirical properties (e.g., "shown to be more faithful in prior work"),
1010 practical considerations (e.g., "computationally efficient for our architecture"),
1011 or systematic comparison goals (e.g., "we benchmark multiple methods to assess
1012 robustness").
1013 - Statements like "we use X" or "X is a popular method" without a reason do NOT count.
1014 - If the paper uses multiple methods as a deliberate comparison/benchmark, that framing
1015 itself counts as a justification.
1016
1017 **Verification output**: "yes", "no", or "unclear", with the supporting quote or
1018 explanation.
1019
1020 ---
1021 ##### Field 4: validation_types
1022
1023 - For each validation type in the extraction, verify that the paper actually performs
1024 that type of validation on the IML outputs (not on the ML model's predictions).
1025 - Key distinction: validating that a model predicts well (e.g., AUROC on test set) is
1026 NOT validation of IML outputs. Validation of IML outputs means checking whether the
1027 explanations are correct, faithful, or biologically meaningful.
1028 - Check for validation types that are present in the paper but MISSING from the
1029 extraction.
1030 - Use only these categories: "visual_inspection", "querying_databases",
1031 "synthetic_datasets", "wet_lab_experiments", "others", "none".
1032
1033 **Verification output**: Corrected list, with a brief note for each type explaining
1034 what the paper actually does.
1035
1036 ---
1037 ##### Field 5: num_successful_instances
1038
1039 - Count the number of distinct, individually presented examples where the authors show
1040 that an IML output aligns with known biology or expected behavior.
1041 - Count figures, subfigures, or text descriptions that each present a separate case.
1042 - Do NOT count aggregate statistics (e.g., "average overlap across 1000 sequences") as
1043 individual instances -- those count as 0 individual instances.
1044 - If the count is 6 or more, output "6+".
1045 - If ambiguous, output "unclear".
1046
1047 **Verification output**: Corrected count, with a brief justification of how you counted.
```

```
1045 ---
1046
1047 ##### Field 6: failure_reported
1048
1049 - Search the paper for any discussion of cases where the IML method failed, produced
1050   unexpected results, or did not align with known biology.
1051 - Also counts: explicit discussion of limitations specific to the IML outputs (not
1052   general model limitations).
1053 - Does NOT count: authors framing unexpected results as "novel findings" or
1054   "interesting observations" without acknowledging them as potential failures.
1055
1056 **Verification output**: "yes" or "no", with the supporting passage or explanation.
1057
1058 ---
1059 ##### Field 7: failure_description
1060
1061 - If failure_reported is "yes", provide a concise summary of the failure.
1062 - If "no", output "none".
1063 - Verify that the description accurately reflects what the paper says -- do not
1064   exaggerate or understate.
1065
1066 **Verification output**: Corrected description or "none".
1067
1068 ---
1069 ### Final Output
1070
1071 After verifying all 7 fields, produce your output in the following JSON format:
1072
1073 {
1074   "verified_extraction": {
1075     "iml_methods": [...],
1076     "iml_method_count": ...,
1077     "iml_justification": "yes" | "no" | "unclear",
1078     "validation_types": [...],
1079     "num_successful_instances": ...,
1080     "failure_reported": "yes" | "no",
1081     "failure_description": "... | "none"
1082   },
1083   "changes_made": [
1084     "Describe each change you made, e.g.: 'Removed X from iml_methods because it was
1085     only mentioned in related work, not applied.'"
1086   ],
1087   "confidence": "high" | "medium" | "low"
1088 }
1089
1090 Rules:
1091 - If you find NO errors, return the original extraction unchanged under
1092   "verified_extraction" and set "changes_made" to ["No changes needed."].
1093 - If you are unsure about a field, err on the side of "unclear" rather than guessing.
1094 - The "confidence" field reflects your overall confidence in the final verified
1095   extraction: "high" means all fields have clear textual support; "medium" means 1-2
1096   fields required judgment calls; "low" means significant ambiguity remains.
1097
1098
1099
```